

MARINE SOUNDSCAPE ECOSYSTEMS AT RISK: A DATA-DRIVEN SPATIAL-SOUND INTERACTIVE EXPERIENCE TO RAISE AWARENESS

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces the immersive interactive installation *504 Ways Of Listening* and its underlying software *Data Driven Multiverse Manipulation* to explore new pathways to public awareness towards anthropogenic noise pollution in marine environments. By developing a system for mapping complex datasets into three dimensional sensory environments, this installation probes new perspectives on how marine soundscapes can be interpreted, represented and experienced.

Data Driven Multiverse Manipulation is a state-of-the-art framework designed to explore and decode the hidden acoustic structures of underwater ecosystems. Through this software, this installation processes passive acoustic recordings dataset provided by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) bioacoustics laboratory using adaptive normalization algorithms, statistical analysis, dimensionality reduction, quantization techniques, interaction design and High-Order Ambisonics to organize the data within an interactive multi-dimensional acoustic space.

In response to the growing ecological urgency posed by anthropogenic noise in marine ecosystems, *504 Ways Of Listening* advocates for environmental awareness through the practice of listening, promoting new forms of engagement with the ocean's acoustic narratives and the ecological issues they reveal.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Significance of Natural Soundscapes and the Impact of Anthropogenic Noise in Marine Environments

Sound plays a pivotal role in the lives of many marine species, serving as a primary means of communication, navigation and environmental awareness. Many marine organisms rely on acoustic signals to locate mates, detect predators and coordinate group behaviors. The natural

symphony of an ecosystem, often referred to as its soundscape, is thus integral to the health and functionality of its inhabitants.

However, the intrusion of anthropogenic (human-made) noise has increasingly disrupted these natural soundscapes, posing significant challenges to marine life [1]. Activities such as shipping, construction and energy exploration introduce substantial underwater noise. A study modeling the underwater sound of floating offshore wind farms in the Central Mediterranean Sea highlighted concerns about the potential impacts of such noise on marine life, emphasizing the need for careful assessment and mitigation strategies [2]. Other sources—such as shipping traffic and oil and gas exploration—have been linked to changes in distribution and behavior across marine species. [3–6].

The consequences of these altered soundscapes are profound and multifaceted. Anthropogenic noise can mask crucial biological sounds [7], leading to increased stress [8], disrupted mating calls [9] and impaired predator-prey interactions. In some cases, species may abandon habitats that have become acoustically inhospitable, leading to reduced biodiversity.

Acoustic monitoring has become essential to detect and understand these disruptions. Research on the acoustic environment of marine mammals has shown that noise pollution affects their ability to communicate and detect environmental cues [10], further highlighting the importance of preserving natural soundscapes. The study of fish bioacoustic diversity in Fiji's back-reef habitats demonstrated the importance of passive acoustic monitoring in understanding community dynamics and the fragility of these ecosystems [11]. Additionally, observed disruptions in dolphin communication have been directly linked to the documented negative impacts on animal fitness [12, 13].

1.2 Citizen engagement

Mitigating the impact of anthropogenic noise requires a multifaceted approach: beyond the adoption of quieter technologies, the implementation of acoustic regulations and the establishment of protected areas, it is essential to act on a cultural level by promoting a renewed culture of listening and sound awareness. Sound, in fact, is not only a medium for environmental analysis: it is a shared mate-

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rial, a common territory between humans and non-humans and can become a powerful tool for reconnecting with the marine environment.

With a 2030 target, the EU Mission *Restore our Ocean and Waters* aims to protect and restore the ocean health through research, innovation and citizen engagement [14]. Its emphasis on the ocean as a unified system aligns with our approach, which situates listening as a participatory practice—both sensory and cultural—that cultivates ecological awareness. In this context, our work is not simply a representational gesture but a proposal for situated sensory engagement: a form of active participation that recognizes listening as a political, aesthetic and epistemological practice capable of generating shared ecological value. Building on research into how acoustic pollution has transformed both marine and terrestrial soundscape ecosystems, along with human perceptual habits [15, 16], our project prototypes an interface for interacting with a multidimensional underwater dataset in an immersive, embodied and intuitive way.

1.3 504 WAYS OF LISTENING

In this paper, we introduce 504 Ways of Listening (504) by Author1, a multimedia project comprising an immersive installation and its software framework, Data Driven Multiverse Manipulation (DDMM)¹. This interactive artwork is conceived to be navigated by a single performer at a time, through a control station positioned within an Ambisonics speaker dome, which is shared with an audience of listeners. The Ambisonics technique envelops the listeners in a three-dimensional sonic sphere, rendering the depths of the underwater world palpably present—, enabling spatialized playback of underwater recordings in a way that mimics the real-world relations of acoustic features into an immersive 3D field. The performer, seated at the center, manipulates this acoustic environment through embodied interaction. In this context, sound is not merely a conduit for information—it becomes an experiential medium for navigating the dynamics and layered complexity of marine acoustic environments (see Figure1).

Thanks to the Italian National Research Council (CNR) and its high-fidelity hydrophone recordings, we have access to extensive datasets from otherwise inaccessible marine environments. These recordings provide rare access to underwater acoustic ecologies that are otherwise difficult to perceive, forming the empirical basis for our installation’s audio content and structure. The development unfolds in two phases: one asynchronous, focused on preparing and analyzing the data and one real-time, dedicated to sound synthesis and interactive control—detailed in the Methodology section. Interaction with 504 unfolds in a blindfolded state, with the performer’s vision entirely

¹ The term “Multiverse”, employed here with poetic license, finds its meaning in the potential to observe multiple permutations of audio feature configurations. Each permutation yields a distinct spatial arrangement of audio data within the acoustic environment—thus generating a unique possible “Universe.” In the title “504 Ways of Listening,” the number 504 refers to the total number of permutations derived from distributing nine identified audio features across the three Cartesian axes—*xyz*. These features include: RMS energy, spectral centroid, spectral bandwidth, zero crossing rate, spectral contrast, chroma, pitch, onset strength and spectral density.

blinded. Through a Virtual Reality (VR) headset, repurposed solely as a gyroscopic sensor, the performer determines their direction of observation. Seated on a rotating chair, they operate a digital Braille keyboard, where the hexagrammatic keys become directional controls within the acoustic universe.

504 thus invites reflection on how acoustic recordings—whether environmental, biological, or relational—can transcend their role as mere data and be reimagined as cultural material. Recent studies have shown, for instance, that the songs of humpback whales exhibit statistical patterns comparable to those of human language [17, 18], suggesting that these soundscapes are not simply natural noise, but complex semiotic systems to be listened to, perceived, and revered. Can art allow us to feel our way into such systems—those that rationality alone may fail to grasp—through practices of deep, embodied listening?

2. METHOD

In this section, we provide a detailed description of the Data Driven Multiverse Manipulation (DDMM) software framework, developed by Author1 and Author2 and its functionalities, which are structured in two main phases: an offline phase, primarily dedicated to the analysis of audio recordings (dataset) and a real-time phase focused on managing the Ambisonics sphere and reading the analysis data. These two phases reflect the conceptual and technical split between preparing underwater acoustic data for interaction and enabling its real-time re-composition into an immersive, navigable sound field. Each step—from segmentation to spatialization—contributes to transforming raw ecological recordings into a perceptual interface for listening-as-engagement.

2.1 Framework overview

This framework was developed using the programming languages Python and MaxMSP, along with the REAPER software.

The choice of Python as the programming language for the offline operations stems from its strong suitability for dataset analysis, including audio data, thanks to its extensive ecosystem of specialized libraries, such as NumPy, Librosa, Pydub and SciPy, which we employed. Additionally, Python features a simple and readable syntax and offers widely adopted tools for Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, which are among the future developments planned for DDMM.

MaxMSP proves to be the optimal choice for real-time operations, as it is a powerful environment for creating interactive applications in the audio field, from music to multimedia arts. It features a visual programming environment that is immediate and modifiable in real time, valued for its flexibility in processing audio and MIDI signals and in the interactive control of sound, video and physical devices. Its modular and performance-oriented nature makes it both a creative and technical tool.

Figure 1. The prototype of 504 Ways of Listening in a sketch, with a dome of 23 speakers and the control platform.

Moreover, it includes powerful libraries for handling complex multichannel techniques, such as Ambisonics via *Spat~* by IRCAM and it offers the ability to write sample-level optimized algorithms using *Gen~*, a MaxMSP subsystem that compiles code to reduce latency and improve efficiency.

Within the digital audio workstation REAPER, the decoding phase of the Ambisonics signals generated with *Spat~* is managed using the IEM audio plugin suite. This phase is efficiently handled by REAPER, which is particularly lightweight, versatile and well-suited for flexible multichannel signal routing. The following sections detail the DDMM processes developed in Python, for the offline normalization, segmentation, analysis, dimensionality reduction and standardization and the real-time processes developed in MaxMSP and REAPER for Ambisonics navigation. Together, these tools allow us to bridge low-level signal features (like energy and spectral shape) with real-time spatial and perceptual effects—supporting the artistic goal of turning environmental sound data into embodied navigational experiences.

2.2 Data origin

The audio archives of the Bioacoustics Laboratory for Marine Environmental Monitoring of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) were collected at the sites of Capo Granitola (Sicily, Italy) and Ny-Ålesund in the Svalbard Islands (Norway).

The acoustic data collection was carried out using an acquisition system consisting of a calibrated hydrophone (model 8104, Brüel & Kjær) with a sensitivity of 205.6 dB re 1 V/ μ Pa \pm 4.0 dB in the frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 80 kHz. The hydrophones were connected to a digital acquisition board (USGH416HB, Avisoft Bioacoustics) with a preamplifier (gain of 40 dB), managed by the software Avisoft Recorder USGH (Avisoft Bioacoustics). The hydrophones were positioned at a depth of 16 meters over a seabed of 45 meters at the Capo Granitola site and at 75 meters depth over an 83-meter seabed at the Svalbard site. Acoustic signals were acquired at a sampling rate of 300,000 samples per second at 16-bit resolution.

The datasets selected for testing DDMM and presented in this paper were converted into 16-bit WAV format with a sampling rate of 48 kHz to reduce computational load and file size, though this limited the analysis range to 0–24 kHz. These acoustic data were recorded at the Capo Granitola site on the following dates: July 26th and August 8th 2018; May 26th, June 26th, September 26th, October 26th and December 26th 2020; May 8th, June 26th, July 26th and August 8th 2021

The datasets are organized into daily directories containing 2-minute-long audio files recorded every 30 minutes, for a total of 48 files per day. The filename of each file in the dataset includes timestamp information about the date and time of the recording, which is preserved throughout the subsequent segmentation and analysis phases to facili-

tate the temporal tracking of acoustic events.

These datasets exhibit very low amplitude levels, with an average RMS value of -52 dBFS, an average peak value of -21 dBFS, -55 LUFS² and an average DC offset of 0.7%.

2.3 Normalisation

In light of the characteristics of the datasets, a preparatory normalization phase is necessary to adjust the RMS value and correct any DC offset, while preserving the dynamic range and spectral content as much as possible. This correction improves both the listening quality of the datasets and the efficiency of feature extraction algorithms in the subsequent analysis phases.

The algorithm developed for this purpose normalizes the datasets by setting a target RMS threshold. Additionally, through a statistical analysis of peaks, it determines whether peak compression is required. This adaptive and automatic behavior allows the algorithm to be applied to a wide range of material, such as recordings made with devices featuring different frequency responses—whether underwater or terrestrial—as well as musical or spoken content, intervening only when the RMS value falls below the target threshold or when a DC offset is detected.

The first evaluation concerns the DC offset: if present, the algorithm applies a high-pass filter (HPF) to remove it. This is followed by an assessment of the RMS value. If the analyzed files have an RMS value below the target threshold, the algorithm evaluates the distribution, density and duration of peaks. These analytical parameters determine the type of processing to be applied, which may consist of either normalization or compression followed by gain adjustment and limiter application to avoid distortion. Compression is applied only if the detected peaks are considered glitches—i.e., shorter than 0.5 ms and sparsely distributed. Otherwise, the peaks are regarded as relevant content to preserve and are only normalized.

The goal of this preparatory phase is to ensure that all audio content within the datasets reaches at least the target RMS value. However, due to this process, the RMS value itself becomes altered in subsequent analysis phases. Nevertheless, as observed during the standardization and dimensionality reduction phases, RMS data still exhibits significant statistical variability during analysis.

2.4 Segmentation

This segmentation phase is intended to divide the already normalized datasets into segments of equal duration. The chosen duration aims to facilitate the reading and management of analysis data by limiting its volume.

It has been observed that a duration of 750 ms (corresponding to a fundamental segmentation frequency of 1.33 Hz) is ideal for analysis data handling. As detailed in the analysis section, this duration allows for 9 analysis windows per segment. However, following the segmentation of the audio files in the datasets, discontinuities may arise at the segment boundaries (start and end). To reduce the

² calculated according to the ITU-R BS.1770-3 standard for loudness measurement

error introduced by FFT analysis on these discontinuities, segmentation includes windowing with a Tukey function with a 50% hop size.

The filenames of the generated segments include a general index, the filename of the original file from which they were extracted (already containing the recording date and time) and the sample numbers marking the start and end of the segment. These elements are useful for tracing the exact position of each segment within the original file.

2.5 Analysis

Once the datasets have been organized into segments, the analysis serves to extract their characteristics (features) and to save the results for use in the subsequent phases of DDMM. The extracted features are chosen among those easiest to read and interpret, taking into account the nature of the datasets and the need to obtain meaningful information for the sonification process. In order to simplify both the interpretation of the analysis data and its later dimensionality reduction, an FFT frame size of 8192 samples with a 50% hop size was selected. This setup yields 9 analysis windows per 750 ms segment, for all descriptors except RMS energy and Spectral density, as explained later.

At the end of the analysis, the algorithm outputs the results in both CSV and WAV format, as discussed in the following paragraphs.

The chosen features are:

- **RMS Energy:** Provides a useful key for better understanding the subsequent features, as it evaluates the intensity of sound events. The output consists of a single magnitude value for each analyzed segment.
- **Zero Crossing Rate:** Ideal for detecting sound events with low or infrasonic fundamental frequencies—such as marine animal vocalizations or anthropogenic noises—through time-domain analysis, which offers higher temporal resolution than FFT-based analyses. This feature is particularly useful in soundscapes rich in low-frequency content, such as underwater environments.
- **Spectral Centroid:** Effective in tracking variations in energy distribution across the spectrum, useful for identifying disturbances and the presence or vocalizations of marine animals.
- **Spectral Bandwidth:** Useful for identifying sound events with significant spectral width, often related to anthropogenic noise such as ship traffic or mining operations. The temporal distribution of these events also provides crucial compositional information about structural shifts and the dynamic balance of marine soundscapes.
- **Spectral Rolloff (High and Low):** Like bandwidth and centroid, these features offer timbral insights helpful in identifying noteworthy sound events for further study or interpretation. Changes in the spectral profile may also help estimate the distance and

direction of a potential sound source, considering the frequency-dependent absorption of sound in water.

- **Chromagram:** Offers a chromatic interpretation of the soundscape, allowing for the observation of melodic and harmonic profiles. For each segment, the analysis data is organized into a matrix with a fixed number of pitch classes (typically 12) as rows and intensity values per FFT frame as columns—making this matrix a potential score guide.
- **Onset Strength:** Extracts amplitude envelopes, which are useful for observing dynamic trends and for use in timbre generation, rhythm extraction, control signal generation and managing the dynamic range in the sonification process.
- **Spectral Density:** Describes the distribution of energy across the FFT bands, enabling developments in clustering and classification, as well as in wavetable synthesis. Additionally, interpreting these values can suggest timbral qualities—sometimes overlapping—and reveal spectral and harmonic relationships within each segment. The output is organized into frequency-density value pairs.

Naturally, the ability to access such an extensive amount of data enables cross-referencing, allowing deeper patterns and correlations to emerge.

The analysis data, already rich in meaning, can reveal an even deeper understanding of the soundscape when combined to form "universes." Each permutation yields a distinct spatial arrangement of audio data within the acoustic environment—thus generating a unique possible "Universe."

2.6 Dimensionality reduction and Standardization

For the formation of these universes and thus the coordinates needed to compose them, it is necessary that each analyzed feature be reduced to a single value, to be used for positioning the segments inside the Ambisonics sphere. These spatial coordinates determine where in the 3D Ambisonics sound field each data segment will be projected—shaping the acoustic landscape that the performer will explore during the installation.

This reduction proves complex due to the presence of heterogeneous data structures, including single values, arrays and matrices, and the need to implement a reversible process to facilitate the reading of analysis data and potential decoding in real-time phases.

Among the various available techniques, such as PCA, t-SNE and binary encoding, the latter seems to best suit our needs with an exact data representation. However, applying this technique requires that the data be quantized, that their range be known and that arrays and matrices do not exceed a certain length to avoid excessively long binary strings in output (for example, over 64 bits). Binary encoding proves useful in this process because it is reversible, given that we know the initial length of arrays, matrices

Table 1. The dataset (see Data origin at chapter 2.2) showing one of the possible Universes, obtained by assigning RMS energy to the *x*-axis, to the point size and to the amount of blue (RGB encoding), Onset Strength to the *y*-axis, Spectral Bandwidth to the *z*-axis and Spectral Density to the scalar *w*. Additionally, Spectral Centroid determines the amount of red and Zero Crossing Rate the amount of green. The effects of the quantization required for binary encoding are also visible as bands of points.

and the value ranges, having properly set the segment duration during segmentation and the FFT frame length during analysis. Finally, reversibility allows us to reconstruct the quantized arrays during real-time phases, to be used as control values and also enables a subsequent implementation of clustering techniques².

In this step, encoded data are standardized to control their distribution and scaled to bring the value domain within the range $[-1, 1]$, domain useful as spatial coordinate.

Below are the processes developed in MaxMSP and REAPER for the real-time management of coordinates in the Ambisonics technique, sound synthesis and navigation of the universes.

2.7 Real time Ambisonics Navigation

Once the spatial coordinates are generated for each segment and each analyzed feature, it is possible to proceed with the real-time creation and observation of the universes by combining 4 features and projecting the segments into a unit-radius sphere. Each “universe” is defined by a specific combination of four acoustic features (e.g., RMS energy, spectral centroid, zero-crossing rate), which determine how the sonic elements are distributed in the 3D sound field. This spatialization enables performers to navigate distinct ecological patterns, perceptible through changes in spatial location, density and timbral color.

The projection is done by normalizing the xyz coordinates and applying a scalar w . This type of projection improves the arrangement of the segments within the Ambisonics sphere (see Table1).

The listener’s position and direction information within the Ambisonics sphere are used to evaluate the distance from the segments and their visibility. These data are useful as control values in sound synthesis, Ambisonics technique management and as a key for interpreting the analysis data.

MaxMSP algorithms in the *Gen~* environment allow reading and decoding the analysis CSVs and coordinates stored in WAV format. As of the writing of this paper, the *buffer~* object, which loads data into memory, is limited to 32-bit addressing. Therefore, it is necessary to split data archives larger than 4 GB.

Also within MaxMSP, *Spat5~*, an advanced Ambisonics library developed by IRCAM, manages the encoding of Ambisonics channels which are then routed via a multichannel virtual audio routing to the REAPER software, where decoding to speakers is handled using the IEM library. The use of this library simplifies decoding operations, the creation and implementation of the decoder via AllRADecoder, the management of LFE (Low Frequency Enclosure) and its filtering with SimpleDecoder, scene rotation with SceneRotator and level monitoring with EnergyVisualizer.

3. DISCUSSION

So far, we have presented the 504 project and the DDMM software, highlighting their aesthetic and technical specificities. We now turn to the critical aspects and the results

Clusters observation

Table 2. This plot illustrates how the binary encoding system affects segment clustering, using a 2-minute slice of the dataset (see Data origin at chapter 2.2) displaying up to 2 kHz in sonogram for easier interpretation. The displayed universe uses RMS energy for the x -axis, point size and amount of blue; Onset Strength for the y -axis; Spectral Bandwidth for the z -axis; Spectral Centroid for the scalar w and the amount of red. Finally, Zero Crossing Rate is used for the amount of green. This combination of features appears effective in clustering sound events composed of impulses, separating them based on the frequency with the greatest energy. In Plot 1, the energy peak is located between 1.7 and 2.1 kHz, while in Plot 2 it lies between 300–500 Hz.

observed up to this point.

3.1 Results

During an initial testing phase of DDMM at the *Electric Audio Unit 2025* event, organized by Eesti Elektroakustiliste Heliloojate Ühing at Elektron.art in Tallinn, several promising perceptual effects and technical chal-

lenges emerged. The critical issues, discussed later, mainly concern the real-time phase. For this occasion, since the synthesis algorithms were still under development, we implemented a playback of the segments with polyphonic granular synthesis, controlling the aforementioned aspects such as Ambisonics encoding, reverberation and so on. Furthermore, during this test, the control interfaces planned for 504 were not used; instead, the position and observation direction were manually controlled. The test took place inside an Ambisonics dome with 23 loudspeakers and an LFE, connected to our computer via the DANTE protocol.

On this occasion, the audience was able to immerse themselves in a vivid representation of the marine soundscape, with all its relationships and behaviors. As previously mentioned, the position, reverberation and all characteristics of the reproduced segments are not the result of arbitrary choices, but are based on the intrinsic features of the data revealed during analysis, as in Table 2. Listeners reported perceiving dynamic shifts in spatial density, spectral texture and source localization—variations that corresponded to changes in the underlying acoustic features. Variations allowed perceiving, for example, how a disturbing element, foreign to that particular sonic ecosystem, influences the entire perceived soundscape. This initial trial suggests that our approach can effectively communicate ecological relationships and disruptions through immersive audio—pointing toward a promising mode of artistic and scientific engagement.

3.2 Limitations

During this research project, we encountered limitations that require further investigation and we expect additional ones to emerge as DDMM and the 504 installation continue to evolve.

A first limitation concerns the source data, which must be processed at high sampling rates to include elements in the ultrasonic range. Acoustic effects such as refraction and channeling make the depth at which hydrophones are positioned crucial for detecting elements present at specific depths (as the SOFAR Channel studies suggest [19]). Moreover, access to historical data is essential to observe changes over time in sonic ecosystems. Finally, relying solely on acoustic data limits the study by excluding other factors influencing the soundscape, such as temperature, salinity and water pressure.

Furthermore, the use of analyses mainly based on FFT entails a time-frequency uncertainty that is not always negligible. Also, segmentation may fragment long-duration sound events, which would then be observed as separate and independent events—a limitation we expect to address through future implementations of clustering techniques.

Lastly, as observed during the Tallinn test, real-time processing requires the development of highly optimized algorithms to limit computational cost, enable scaling to larger datasets and manage multiple sound sources in real time.

3.3 Further developments

The next developments of DDMM focus on the creation of a modular synthesis engine capable of generating more nuanced and ecologically coherent sound textures in real time. We also aim to finalize the interactive control interfaces for 504, enabling embodied navigation through the acoustic universes.

In parallel, we are experimenting with alternative dimensionality reduction and clustering techniques (as proposed by Sainburg Et al. [20]), with the goal of implementing unsupervised learning algorithms that can reveal previously unrecognized patterns. We hypothesize that an open-ended, serendipitous mode of exploring complex datasets could complement current data analysis methods and provide new insights for scientific research, identifying new characteristics of sound ecosystems useful for their preservation.

4. CONCLUSION

Guided by the pleasure of discovery, we have followed an empirical approach that combines intuition and experience from both musical and technical domains. This approach leads us to explore an immensely broad field spanning biology, data science and media art,—one with political, ecological and epistemological implications.

We envision a future in which tools like DDMM can be made accessible beyond specialist contexts, contributing to new ways of listening to and understanding the complexity of the living world.

In this vision, data are not merely numbers to analyze or visualize: they are traces of living reality that cross bodies, territories and relationships. We gather environmental signals—movements invisible to us, hidden within ecosystems that seem distant at first glance—and transform them into immersive sonic experiences. We explore how acoustic data can become cultural material: not only as aesthetic content, but as a vehicle for ecological awareness and sensory participation. We are driven by the desire to rethink data as living material—not just to be analyzed, but to be reactivated, reinterpreted and shared in inclusive, creative and generative forms. We commit to building sustainable spaces and narratives that can expand our capacity for listening and understanding. In doing so, technology becomes a tool to create responsible connections, restoring to both technology and art their role in the service of the common good.

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